

doctorandă, Universitatea de Stat din Moldova

Eugenia **GANEA**

The Particular Situation of Care- Leaving Youth in Vocational/ Technical Education: a Gender- Centered Perspective

Abstract: *The article highlights the vulnerabilities of care-leavers of state alternative care who are making their transition to independent life through vocational/technical education. The situation of girls/young women and the importance of gender education in vocational/technical institutions is specifically*

emphasized and put up for discussion. Our research has found that the transition to adulthood of care-leaving adolescent girls and boys from state alternative care is associated with a number of specific challenges, which can become turning points for these young people, and therefore require special attention, aimed at supporting the youth and creating an environment to help their transition to independent adult life.

Keywords: *female care leavers, state alternative care, gender education, vocational/technical institutions, life skills, risk of*

exploitation, social and education policies.

Rezumat: Articolul elucidează vulnerabilitatea tinerilor care ies din serviciile de îngrijire alternativă de stat și își fac tranziția către viața independentă prin studii în instituții de învățământ profesional tehnic. Se analizează în special situația fetelor și importanța educației de gen în învățământul profesional tehnic. S-a constatat că tranziția către o viață adultă a fetelor și băieților de vârstă adolescentă, care ies din serviciile de îngrijire alternativă de stat, este însoțită de provocări specifice. Aceste provocări pot deveni puncte de cotitură pentru tineri, iată de ce subiectul cere atenție specială, în scopul susținerii acestor tineri și creării unui mediu care să le sprijine tranziția către o viață independentă.

Cuvinte-cheie: fete care ies din serviciile de îngrijire alternativă, îngrijire alternativă de stat, educație de gen, instituții de învățământ profesional tehnic, deprinderi de viață, riscul exploatarei, politici sociale și educaționale.

INTRODUCTION

There is a number of factors that put Moldovan children at risk of abuse, neglect, exploitation, and separation from parents. The latter is often associated with intra-family problems originating from poverty, labor migration, human trafficking, substance abuse, and violence against women and children. 11% of Moldova's children do not live with either of their biological parents, according to the MICS report [1, p. 22]. This means that they are raised in state alternative care or foster families.

According to Ministry statistics, more than 1600 adolescents are leaving alternative care of familiar and institutional type every year: in 2019 alone 1639 children moved out of alternative care [7, p. 14]. Out of this group, comprised of 793 girls and 846 boys, 540 had reached the age of 18 and were therefore preparing to “check out” of the system. 32 girls and boys left alternative care for the reason of being enrolled in vocational/technical education (vocational/technical schools and colleges). 44 young persons were neither enrolled in educational institutions, nor employed [7, p. 14].

THE SPECIFIC DIFFICULTIES FACED BY CARE LEAVERS IN THEIR TRANSITION TO ADULTHOOD

In analyzing the difficulties faced by care leavers, we should be conscious of the fact that autonomous living for any young person implies much more than basic needs – and care leavers usually have to struggle even with their basic needs when they find themselves living autonomously. Undeniably, autonomy comes from different things, from a baggage that is supposed to be full of the skills and knowledge that young people would have normally acquired from their parents. This includes emotional skills, thoughts and feelings that need to be dealt with and which young care leavers are lacking. Therefore, their immediate decisions and choices of what to do can be made in unfortunate circumstances that may determine their whole life as members of society, as those who represent the future of the country.

Based on feedback derived from interviews with

professionals from NGOs working on care-leaving youth support projects, we have found that *girls and boys leaving care* are seriously affected when and after they leave the alternative care system; many find themselves in critical situations and at turning points. Many of these girls and boys do not have an established legal status, such as ‘abandoned’ or ‘temporarily lacking parental care’, and in consequence endure financial difficulties and cannot benefit from governmental allowances. Many do not know how to get an identity card when reaching the appropriate age. Many care leavers enter informal employment; many are tempted to abandon school as soon as they enter an (informal) work arrangement. This pushes them into very difficult situations, exposing them to being exploited, not paid, and, as informal workers, having no medical insurance. When they get ill under such circumstances, and taking into consideration their young age, lack of life experience, and uncertainty about what could be done, the situation becomes really dire.

This kind of situation can be much harder for girls, especially if they end up as teenage single mothers with neither education or the financial means to sustain themselves. NGOs working with young care leavers and adolescents in technical vocational education institutions have discovered that such girls are often exposed to sexual harassment and may become victims of various forms of gender-based violence.

While care leavers are considerably more prone to encounter the downsides of the social, economic, and financial aspects of life, which may affect any young person, the situation is aggravated by the fact that they become invisible to the social protection system once they turn 18, and often even sooner, should they move to a new place in order to pursue education or employment.

Another problem for the girls and boys leaving the alternative care system, especially those from state institutions, is related to lack of career guidance, i.e. admission guidance in order to be able to *intentionally and knowingly* choose their future profession. Most often – especially young people placed in state care instituti-

ons – are collectively enrolled in a vocational/technical school that has traditional links with their care service, and not according to their individual qualifications and interests. As a result, after graduating from such a vocational/technical school these young people often seek to migrate for work outside the country, which is currently problematic due to the travel restrictions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic.

On the side of *stakeholders with a mandate related to social protection of minors*, when girls and boys leave alternative care and move elsewhere to pursue education, the responsibility is ‘lifted’ from those authorities. Moreover, upon the young adults’ reaching of the age of 18 the guardianship authority bears no legal responsibility for tracking and monitoring them. They become invisible to the system, left alone with their own problems, and are thus exposed to the risk of various forms of violence and exploitation.

Furthermore, the girls and boys who get enrolled in vocational/technical education institutions face challenges to integrate in a new environment and would often display frustration and behavior problems. Often this is the reason why they drop out, and neither the guardianship authority, nor the vocational/technical school is apprehensive about them leaving the school with no qualifications and no source of livelihood.

The teachers in vocational/technical schools also face specific difficulties in working with care-leaving teens, since often these young people need more support for learning and some display behavior problems. For example, as part of a pilot project of the NGO AVE Copiii¹, the professionals from this NGO provided psychosocial support, guidance, and mentoring, as well as emotional support to prevent dropouts and ensure that the boy or girl is determined to complete his or her education and obtain a graduation diploma. Another NGO, Gender Centru, conducted in the past training sessions for boys and girls in technical/vocational schools all over the country, under a previous project financially supported by OSCE in Moldova². The training aimed at topics related to the reproductive health of boys and girls, combating harassment, topics related to sexuality and reproductive health for girls only, gender-based violence, and family violence.

A GENDER-SPECIFIC ANALYSIS AND THE IDENTIFIED ISSUES

There are problems and challenges specifically faced by girls and boys, mainly arising from lack of life skills, little knowledge about reproductive health, and behavior problems, which lead to sexual harassment

against girls, teenage pregnancies, and health problems caused by STDs.

According to a national survey on violence against children and young people in the Republic of Moldova, the data for 2019 indicate that one in seven girls (14.4%) and one in twenty boys (5.3%) have suffered sexual violence before the age of 18 [6, p. 39]. Also, one in four teenage girls (25.9%) and one in three teenage boys (35.2%) were subjected to physical violence before reaching the age of 18 [4, p. 45]. The most frequent aggressor in the first incident of sexual abuse of girls was an unknown person (25.6%); while among boys it was a friend (51.3%). Three out of ten (31.3%) girls exposed to sexual abuse as children said that the aggressor was at least five years older than them [6, p. 40].

Based on the feedback provided by the teachers from vocational/technical schools, our research has identified several challenges faced by teachers willing to integrate gender education into the teaching process, such as:

- lack of gender-sensitive teaching and didactic materials: lack of guides, methodological support on mainstreaming gender in the education and training process;
- lack of gender-related competencies in the teaching staff;
- lack of a curriculum and methodology for gender education;
- lack of recommended literature for students in school libraries.

With regard to the gender-related competencies in teaching staff, generalizing different approaches to the taxonomy of competences and taking into account the suggestions of the European Qualifications Framework (2005) and Moldova National Qualifications Framework, certain authors suggest the following classifications of competences for higher education (5, p. 32):

1. According to the degree of generalization:
 - generic;
 - specific.
2. According to the degree of specification and hierarchy:
 - generic:
 - a) key/transversal/transdisciplinary competences – transferable among different domains of study;
 - b) professional for a wide domain of activity, group of professions, specializations – transferable within the respective profile: cognitive and functionally-active.
 - specific:
 - a) professional – specific to a major/to a double major: cognitive and functionally active;
 - b) subjects:
 - general for the said subject;

1 <https://avecopiii.md/serviciul-de-suport-pentru-tineri-ave-copiii/>

2 <https://sp3balti.blogspot.com/2017/05/osce.html?m=1>

- specific to the unit of learning.

At vocational/technical school-level policies and sector level policies:

- School-level charters / regulations do not provide for measures to attract girls and their enrollment in non-traditional trades and sectors, inclusively by the setting of enrolment quotas;
- Lack of gender-sensible budgets in vocational schools. For example, students from cooking vocations have to buy ingredients for practical classes;
- Gender blind or sometimes gender-discriminatory Classifier of Occupations. For example, “seamstress” (cusătoreasă) and “sewer” (cusător) are different occupations, and boys refuse to enroll as “seamstresses”.

Consequently, another gender specific problem in the vocational/technical education system is educational gender segregation.

The professionals from AVE Copiii mentioned that based on their observations, the number of girls leaving care and enrolled in vocational/technical education is significantly smaller than the number of boys. Feedback from interviews with representatives of schools shows that although there is considerable gender segregation by types of professions, these schools have neither designed campaigns nor considered developing incentives to raise awareness and to attract girls.

An analysis of national statistics shows that in the 2019-2020 school year 31% of girls were enrolled in vocational/technical education based on a gymnasium level of education (will be studying for a profession for two years), 20% girls were enrolled in 2-year-long courses, 46% were enrolled in dual education (1-2 years of study), and 58% girls were enrolled in courses based on secondary and lyceum education [3].

These figures suggest that girls prefer to leave their home as late as possible and they choose shorter courses. The fact that most girls are enrolled in dual education suggests that they choose the kind of courses that would give them both practical knowledge and the possibility to learn from a future prospective employer.

This analysis and statistics also indicate that it is necessary to develop projects with vocational/technical institutions involved in dual education, to dedicate efforts to promoting non-traditional occupations for girls, such as electricians, welders, ICT operators, thus breaking gender stereotypes and opening more prospective occupations and income opportunities for girls.

Mainstreaming and promoting gender education in vocational/technical schools would respond to national education policies and the Strategy for the development of vocational/technical education for 2013-2020 [5, p. 12].

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STAKEHOLDERS

Actions are needed from development partners, state authorities responsible for education and social policies, as well as the NGO sector. Such actions should be aimed at increasing the life skills and other abilities of girls and boys leaving care in order to help them cope with the social, economic, and other challenges they face in this transition. It is necessary to increase the cooperation between the relevant authorities mandated with the responsibility for child protection, thus ensuring that the girls and boys leaving care do not become invisible to the child protection system once they leave their place of residence in state alternative care of institutional or familiar type in the rural areas across Moldova.

Building life skills is equally important in both girls and boys leaving state care, since this is a very vulnerable category of young people. However, the gender analysis conducted as part of this research, as well as the observations recorded by the NGOs working with this category of children and adolescents suggest that the girls leaving care may be particularly affected by a lack of life skills, since, in virtue of their gender, they may easily become a target of sexual exploitation or rape. Such girls would often get pregnant and become single mothers as they enter adulthood or even before reaching the age of 18.

Pregnancy and motherhood consequently may cause them to discontinue their schooling and push them into a financial and subsistence crisis. It is necessary to tackle the issue by working directly for and with the girls leaving care and by supporting the relevant authorities and the teaching staff in vocational schools to make them better equipped with strategies and professional skills to support girls. Special training for teaching staff in vocational/technical education on the issue of gender mainstreaming in the education and didactic process is also important.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions of this analysis suggest that stakeholders such as NGOs, donors, and state institutions should tackle the problem of care leavers and help build the girls’ and boys’ resilience against violence by raising awareness and conducting educational activities on sexual and reproductive health. Also, stakeholders should be aware that this category of young people are particularly exposed to the risks of sexual exploitation and are in need of particular support, including psychological counselling. However, the issue needs comprehensive action through targeted projects to tackle the problem more broadly.

Poverty in the country, the unsteady political, economic, and social situation affects all categories of citizens; but it is the financially deprived and those who are denied their rights and who lack life skills that are

in a particularly dire situation. This ultimately has implications not only for their own present and future, but also for the future of the Moldovan society as a whole.

REFERENCES:

1. NGO Alternative Report to the Republic of Moldova. Combined 4th and 5th Periodic Report on the Implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. 2016. 22 p. On: https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/Treaties/CRC/Shared%20Documents/MDA/INT_CRC_NGO_MDA_26229_E.pdf
2. Arends D., Ianachevici M., Nemerenco A., Țurcan A. Children in the Republic of Moldova. Situation Analysis 2016. On: <https://www.unicef.org/moldova/media/2511/file/SITAN-UNICEF-Moldova-2016.pdf>
3. Biroul Național de Statistică. Activitatea instituțiilor de învățământ profesional tehnic în anul de studii 2019/20. On: <https://statistica.gov.md/newsview.php?l=ro&idc=168&id=6532>
4. Guțu V. et al. Cadrul de referință al Curriculumului Universitar. Chișinău: CEP USM, 2015.
5. Hotărârea Guvernului nr. 97/2013 cu privire la aprobarea Strategiei de dezvoltare a învățământului vocațional/tehnic pe anii 2013-2020. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 31-35, 2013.
6. Organizația Internațională pentru Migrație (OIM) și IMAS, și Centrul pentru Controlul și Prevenirea Maladiilor. Violența împotriva copiilor și tinerilor în Republica Moldova: constatările unui sondaj național, 2019. Chișinău: Ministerul Sănătății, Muncii și Protecției Sociale, 2019.
7. Raportul statistic (anual) nr. 103. Copii aflați în situație de risc și copii separați de părinți, completat cu datele obținute de la structurile teritoriale de asistență socială. On: <https://msmps.gov.md/sites/default/files/>